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Title: Start-up performance of anaerobic digestion versus co-digestion including the insight of the active microbiome

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Abstract: The aim of this study is to assess the performance of anaerobic digestion against co-digestion systems during the start-up stages based on key process parameters and biological indicators. Two parallel experiments treating sewage sludge alone or co-digested with low concentration of pig manure (8% vol., 2-3% in COD basis) were carried out in two lab-scale CSTR at mesophilic conditions. Same inoculant and organic loading rate sequences were applied for two consecutive runs of 79 and 90 days. According to the removal efficiencies achieved, no significant differences were encountered amongst mono-digestion and co-digestion. This observation was reinforced with the analysis of the total/active microbiome, sequencing 16S rRNA genes and transcripts. The addition of a co-substrate at low concentration had a negligible effect on the total/active microbial communities; they evolved following the same pattern. This might be an advantage in order to upgrade existing wastewater treatment plants to become centralized biogas facilities.

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Highlights

- Start-up of mono-digestion and co-digestion achieved similar process performances
- Low-concentrated co-substrate has a slight effect on total/active microbiome
- *Thermotogae* bacteria were favored over time in both AD and AcoD systems

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1 **Start-up performance of anaerobic digestion versus co-digestion including the insight**
2 **of the active microbiome**

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4 **24 Abstract**

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6 **25** The aim of this study is to assess the performance of anaerobic digestion against co-
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8 **26** digestion systems during the start-up stages based on key process parameters and biological
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10 **27** indicators. Two parallel experiments treating sewage sludge alone or co-digested with low
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12 **28** concentration of pig manure (8% vol., 2-3% in COD basis) were carried out in two lab-
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14 **29** scale CSTR at mesophilic conditions. Same inoculant and organic loading rate sequences
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16 **30** were applied for two consecutive runs of 79 and 90 days. According to the removal
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18 **31** efficiencies achieved, no significant differences were encountered amongst mono-digestion
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20 **32** and co-digestion. This observation was reinforced with the analysis of the total/active
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22 **33** microbiome, sequencing 16S rRNA genes and transcripts. The addition of a co-substrate at
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24 **34** low concentration had a negligible effect on the total/active microbial communities; they
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26 **35** evolved following the same pattern. This might be an advantage in order to upgrade
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28 **36** existing wastewater treatment plants to become centralized biogas facilities.
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36 **37 Keywords**

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38 Anaerobic Digestion, Co-digestion, Start-up, Active microbiome, next-generation
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41 **Abbreviations:** AcoD: anaerobic co-digestion; AD: anaerobic digestion; ASV: amplicon
42 sequence variants; BMP: biochemical methane potential; cDNA: complementary
43 deoxyribonucleic acid; COD: chemical oxygen demand; CSTR: continuous stirred-tank
44 reactor; FOG: fat, oil and grease; HRT: hydraulic retention time; IA: intermediate
45 alkalinity; IA/TA: alkalinity ratio; OLR: organic loading rate; PA: partial alkalinity;
46 PCoA: principal coordinate analysis; PM: pig manure; PS: primary sludge; RT: reverse
47 transcriptase; SS: sewage sludge; TA: total alkalinity; TKN: total Kjeldahl nitrogen; TS:
48 total solids; UASB: up-flow anaerobic sludge blanket; VFA: volatile fatty acids; VS:
49 volatile solids; WAS: waste activated sludge; WWTP: wastewater treatment plant

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4 **50 1. Introduction**

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6 51 Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a process catalyzed by a mixed microbial culture, highly
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8 52 diverse and dynamic, which converts the organic matter into methane-containing biogas in
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10 53 the absence of an external electron acceptor. According to Kleerebezem and van
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12 54 Loosdrecht (2007), the development of bioprocesses using undefined mixed cultures can
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14 55 only be based on natural/ecological selection, driven by the manipulation of the operating
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16 56 conditions or by modifying the source of the inoculum. Particularly, the start-up of AD can
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18 57 be very tedious (two to four months or longer in UASB reactors) before reaching a steady-
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20 58 state condition due to the slow growth of microorganisms (Steyer et al., 2006). Mesophilic
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22 59 digesters reportedly exhibited successful start-up by relying on aerobic and anaerobic
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24 60 wastewater sludge and cattle manure as inoculant (Maroun and El Fadel, 2007).
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26 61 Traditionally, a stepwise adaptation of AD microbial communities to stressful conditions
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28 62 (high organic loading rates (OLR), low hydraulic retention time (HRT), temperature
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30 63 fluctuations, high ammonium concentration or acid content) has been used to strengthen the
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32 64 microbiome against future disturbances (Carballa et al., 2015). Notwithstanding, the
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34 65 stability of AD processes was often measured by practitioners in terms of macroscopic
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36 66 effects, leaving the microbial communities as a ‘black box’ (Koch et al., 2014; Wiese and
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38 67 König, 2009).
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40 68 Recent studies on microbial ecology showed some correspondences among the AD
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42 69 performance and ecological parameters such as evenness of microbial community structure,
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44 70 microbiome diversity and dynamics of microbial community over time. For instance,
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46 71 Ferguson et al. (2018) highlighted that a more equitable distribution of diversity in AD is
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48 72 related to higher methane content in the gas. Regueiro et al. (2015), who studied the
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50 73 dynamics of microbial communities during organic and hydraulic overloads, found clear
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4 74 correlations among the changes on the operating conditions and the microscopic shifts.
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6 75 More recently, Kurade et al. (2019) observed a significant α -diversity change of the
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8 76 acetoclastic methanogens along the operation of an anaerobic co-digestion (AcoD) system
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10 77 treating sewage sludge and fat, oil and grease (FOG) for 120 days.
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14 78 On the other hand, Zhang et al. (2014), after reviewing the characteristics of 78 anaerobic
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16 79 digester samples from 28 references, concluded that the phylogenetic structure was mostly
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18 80 affected by the type of substrate rather than by environmental factors or reactor
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20 81 configuration; furthermore, this effect prevailed as a continuum for which microbiomes
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22 82 from co-digestion systems fall between the blended substrate types. According to this, the
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24 83 adoption of anaerobic co-digestion might entail not only positive interactions in terms of
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26 84 macro- and micronutrient equilibrium, moisture balance and/or dilute inhibitory or toxic
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28 85 compounds (Mata-Alvarez et al., 2014), but also a higher microbial diversity coming from
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30 86 each co-substrate. Thanks to the complimentary characteristics of the different substrates,
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32 87 co-digestion might improve the profitability of existing treatment plants due to higher
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34 88 energy recovery as biogas (Hagos et al., 2017).
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38 89 Based on the results aforementioned, it is still challenging to find consistent relationships
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40 90 among AD or AcoD performances and microbial community structure. Overall,
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42 91 *Proteobacteria*, *Firmicutes*, *Bacteroidetes*, *Actinobacteria* and *Chloroflexi* are the major
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44 92 bacterial phyla in anaerobic digester (De Vrieze et al., 2018; Nelson et al., 2011; Rivière et
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46 93 al., 2009), whose diversity is mainly driven by the use of different substrates and
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48 94 operational conditions such as temperature or OLR. On the contrary, the archaeal
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50 95 population is driven by environmental factors, mainly the concentrations of volatile fatty
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52 96 acids (VFA), ammonium, and temperature, as well as by reactor configuration (Carballa et
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54 97 al., 2015). So far, only few studies exist about microbial diversity in AcoD system (Koo et
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98 al., 2019) and even less studies on active microbiome (Amha et al., 2017). The
99 investigation of the active microbial community in AcoD and AD is however of major
100 interest in order to go deeper into the microorganism interactions in these systems (De
101 Vrieze et al., 2018). Particularly, it would help to describe the dynamics of the bacterial and
102 archaeal communities involved in AD or AcoD systems.
103 This study aims at comparing the performance and active microbiome dynamics of both
104 mono-digestion and co-digestion systems during the start-up stages, treating sewage sludge
105 (SS) alone or co-digested with pig manure (PM). The analysis comprises the calculation of
106 typical key process indicators associated with the amplicon sequencing of the 16S rRNA
107 genes and transcripts. The main objective is to demonstrate whether or not the addition of a
108 co-substrate at low concentrations has a real impact on the process performance, and if the
109 outcome can be correlated with a key biological indicator.

110 **2. Materials and Methods**

111 **2.1 Experimental set-up**

112 The experiments for the start-up of AcoD and AD systems were carried out in parallel lab-
113 scale CSTR at mesophilic conditions (37 °C). In one reactor, steady blends of sewage
114 sludge (SS; 92.15 % vol.) and pig manure (PM; 7.85 % vol.) were treated under AcoD; in
115 the second unit, SS alone under AD. The blend of residues was chosen intentionally, to
116 study a plausible scenario where a full-scale wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) could
117 include the co-digestion process, treating mainly SS with up to 7 – 8 % of PM as a co-
118 substrate (% vol.). Two consecutive experiments of 79 and 90 days were performed for
119 each AcoD and AD setups, at loading rates of 1.6 – 2.4 gVS/L d (equivalent to 2.41 – 3.63
120 gCOD/L d). A stepwise increase of OLR was applied every 20 days. The experiments
121 concluded when the system achieved the steady-state condition. After the end of the first

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122 run (0 – 79 days), digesters remained idle for four days before starting the second set of
123 experiments for 90 more days (83 – 173 days of operation) on the same corresponding
124 CSTR.

125 The experimental set-up consists of two double-walled stainless-steel reactors heated at 37
126 °C with a regulated heating circulator (Julabo CORIO C immersion circulator). The total
127 volume of the digesters was 14.5 L, with an effective volume of 13 L. Initially, the CSTR
128 were inoculated with 13 L of anaerobic sludge from La Farfana WWTP (Santiago, Chile),
129 from a full-scale digester operating at 1.6 – 1.7 gVS/L d. Feeding was carried out daily in a
130 semi-continuous mode from the top of the reactor; draining and sampling, from a side-wall
131 port. Each unit was equipped with a two-straight-blade stirrer (OS20-S LED Digital
132 Overhead stirrer) set at 200 rpm. Gas outlets passed through a water trap before going into
133 the flowmeters. The biogas production (volume) was measured every 1 min with a
134 Milligascounter MGC-1 (Ritter gas meter), and gas outputs were logged in a data
135 acquisition software (Ritter Rigamo).

136 **2.2 Substrates**

137 The sewage sludge was collected from La Farfana WWTP (Santiago, Chile). It was
138 prepared on-site from the mix of primary sludge (PS; 50 % vol.) and waste activated sludge
139 (WAS; 50 % vol.) from the same plant. Pig manure was taken from a local farm. Table 1
140 shows an average characterization of these residues.

141 --- (Table 1) ---

142 In the first set of experiments, SS was diluted with water when needed (and amended with
143 NaHCO₃ to meet the original buffer capacity of the substrate) to obtain a steady organic
144 content of 47.2 gCOD/L. The second experiment treated the raw SS taken from the WWTP
145 (having on average 66.5 g COD/L for the entire operation).

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4 **146 2.3 Analytical Methods**

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6 147 Parameters such as COD, pH, partial and total alkalinity (PA, TA), N-NH₃ content, TKN,
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8 148 total and volatile solids (TS, VS), were measured off-line following *Standard Methods*
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10 149 (APHA, 2012). Particularly, COD content was determined with the Colorimetric Method,
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12 150 and N-NH₃ with the manual Phenate Method. Gas composition (CH₄ and CO₂) was
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14 151 analyzed using a gas chromatograph (PerkinElmer, Clarus® 500), equipped with a thermal
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16 152 conductivity detector (TCD). 250 µL of headspace sample were manually injected with a
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18 153 gas tight syringe (SGE Analytical Science) on a Teflon column (dimensions L ×OD× ID,
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20 154 10 ft × 1/8 in × 2.1 mm) packed with HayeSep Q, 80/100 mesh (Supelco, Bellafonte, USA).
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22 155 The column was heated at 70 °C and maintained for 4 min. Helium was used as carrier gas,
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24 156 flowing at 25 ml/min. The temperature of the injector and detector were set to 80 °C and
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26 157 120 °C, respectively. Standard gas mixture composed of 50.0 % H₂, 5.0 % N₂, 15.0 % CH₄
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28 158 and 30.0 % CO₂ (Linde gas, Chile) was injected in triplicate (associated error: 4.73%
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30 159 deviation) at each measurement series to correct the potential analytical deviation.
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32 160 The biochemical methane potential (BMP) of each waste was determined with a series of
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34 161 four batches. The tests were carried out in the same CSTR reactors after the completion of
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36 162 the second set of the continuous experiments. This ensured the presence of an active and
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38 163 acclimated biomass. In addition, a substrate to biomass ratio (F/M) of 0.4 was applied to
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40 164 shorten the length of the tests and guarantee the activity of the biomass for the remaining
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42 165 assays of the series. Finally, accurate follow-up of biogas production over time was
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44 166 achieved by logging every one minute the biogas volume counted by increments of 3 mL,
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46 167 which it stands for to the degradation of approximately 0.5 mg COD/L in the 13 L reactors.
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48 168 A detailed description if these batch assays is shown in the *Supplementary Material*.
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4 **169 2.4 Nucleic Acid Extraction**

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6 170 The samples for nucleic acid extraction were collected every 20 days including both the
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9 171 starting and completion dates of all experiments (sampling of first run: days 0, 20, 40, 60,
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11 172 79; second run: days 83, 103, 123, 143, 173). They all remained stored at -80°C until
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13
14 173 nucleic acid extraction. RNA and DNA were co-extracted for each sampling point (see
15
16 174 Figure 1) in duplicate (n = 41 for RNA and n= 41 for DNA) using between 1.76-3.52 g of
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19 175 liquid nitrogen-frozen sludge sample using a Power Soil© Total RNA Isolation Kit
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21 176 (QIAGEN, CA, USA) with the RNA Power Soil© DNA elution accessory kit following the
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23 177 manufacturer's recommendations. Isolated nucleic acids were quantified and purity was
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26 178 checked using a BioSpec-nano micro-volume UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu,
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29 179 USA). Resulting total RNA concentrations ranged between 213 and 4501 ng/μL and DNA
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31 180 ranged between 573 and 3,052 ng/μL. Genomic DNA was removed from RNA extracts
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33 181 using the DNaseI (RNase-free, New England, Biolab) and removal of gDNA was
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36 182 confirmed with no amplification using the DGGE300F (5'-GCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAG-
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38 183 3') (Muyzer et al., 1993) and Univ516R (5'-GTDTTACCGCGG CKGCTGRCA-3')
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41 184 (Takai and Horikoshi, 2000) primers by qPCR. The RNA samples were then reverse
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43 185 transcribed with random primers using Affinity Script qPCR cDNA synthesis (Stratagene),
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46 186 thus obtaining 30 ng cDNA/μL for all samples and stored at -80°C until use.
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48 187 --- (Figure 1) ---

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50 **188 2.5 Library preparation and amplicon sequencing of bacterial and archaeal 16S rRNA**
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52 **189 gene and transcripts**

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55 190 A total of 17 DNA samples (for DNA, only samples from substrates SS and PM, inoculum
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58 191 and both initial and end dates of the experiments were selected for sequencing) and 41
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60 192 cDNA samples (including SS, PM, inoculum and time series from both AD and ACoD
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4 193 reactors) were selected for high throughput sequencing (Figure 1). The V4 region of the
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6 194 16S rRNA and rDNA libraries were amplified using 520F (5'-AYTGGGYDTAAAGNG-
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9 195 3') and 802R (5'-TACNNGGGTATCTAATCC-3') primers (Claesson et al., 2009) with the
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11 196 RANGER mix (Bioline, UK). The thermal program consisted in an initial step 5 min at
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14 197 95°C, then 35 cycles of 30 sec at 94°C, 30 sec at 55°C and 90 sec at 72°C using GenePro
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16 198 thermal cycler (Hangzhou Bioer Technology). Resulting amplification was load on a 1.2%
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19 199 (w/v) agarose gel and purified using the Zymoclean™ Gel DNA Recovery kit (Zymo, US).
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21 200 Massive sequencing was performed on an Ion Torrent PGM (Life Technologies) at the
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24 201 platform at the Biological Research Institute “Clemente Estable” (Montevideo, Uruguay).
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26 202 Quantitative assessment of the libraries was analyzed by Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit
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29 203 (Qubit™). Emulsion amplification of the library was performed using Ion Onetouch 2
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31 204 System with the Ion PGM Template OT2 Hi-Q view 400 kit (Pub. No. MAN0014579). Ion
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34 205 Sphere Particles (ISPs) enrichment step was performed on the Ion OneTouch ES system
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36 206 (Pub. No. MAN0014579). The Ion PGM system was used for sequencing using Ion PGM
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39 207 Hi-Q view Sequencing Solutions and Ion 316 Chip v2, following the manufacturer's
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41 208 recommended protocol for 400 bp reads (Pub. No. MAN0014583).

42 43 209 **2.6 Bioinformatic Analysis**

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45 210 Sequence analysis was performed using ‘quantitative insights into microbial ecology’
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48 211 pipeline (QIIME2 2019.7.0 release) (Bolyen et al., 2019) with additional analyses
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50 212 performed using R. Multiplexed single-end sequencing reads (9,873,626 in total) were
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53 213 imported into the QIIME2. The ‘divisive amplicon denoising algorithm’ DADA2 (Callahan
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55 214 et al., 2016) plugin in QIIME2 was used to ‘denoise’ sequencing reads. This step filters out
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58 215 noise and corrects errors in marginal sequences, removes chimeric sequences and
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60 216 singletons and finally dereplicates the resulting sequences, resulting in high resolution
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217 amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) for downstream analysis. This resulted in 7,085,432
218 sequences ranging from 13,277 to 962,746 per sample (n=59 in total) representing 7,600
219 ASVs. The consensus sequences for the ASVs were classified with a classify-sklearn
220 classifier trained against the most recent SILVA 16S rRNA gene reference (release 132)
221 database (Quast et al., 2012). Because of low sequence number, two samples (i.e. no-RT
222 negative control and E2R2-2a) were removed from the dataset for further analysis. In order
223 to complete downstream diversity and composition analyses, sequences were rarefied to the
224 lowest number of sequences per sample (n= 55,971 sequences). This resulted in a total of
225 3,190,347 sequences in the dataset representing 7,199 ASVs (5.3% of total ASVs were
226 removed).

227 **2.7 Statistical Analysis**

228 All the statistical analysis was performed in R version 3.5.1 (R Core Team, 2013) with R
229 Studio environment Version 1.0.153. The filtered *biom* file from QIIME2 was imported and
230 analyzed through *phyloseq*-modified workflow (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013).
231 Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity matrix of non-
232 transformed relative abundance diversity datasets (cDNA and DNA separately, with n=41
233 and n=17 samples, respectively) were used in order to visualize the distribution of the
234 microbial composition. After variance homogeneity check (*betadisper* function of the
235 ‘vegan’ package, (Oksanen et al., 2013), permutational ANOVA was used to identify the
236 significant segregation of samples according to explicative factor A third PCoA was
237 performed considering only AD and AcoD experiments (n= 33 samples) in order to
238 decipher discrepancies between AcoD and AD experiment. An envfit analysis (*envfit*
239 function used with 10,000 permutations, ‘vegan’ package, Oksanen et al. (2013) was
240 associated to the last PCoA in order to identify the significant operational parameters that

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241 can explain the active microbial composition distribution. The ASVs that significantly
242 changed between the first experiment and the second experiment were estimated by the
243 differential transcript abundance (based on the negative binomial distribution, *DESeq*
244 function of the ‘DESeq2’ package, (Love et al., 2014). The significant change in 16S rRNA
245 transcript abundance between the two experiments was expressed through the
246 log2FoldChange. Forward selection allowed identify the best predictor of the
247 methanogenic archaeal distribution (*forward.sel* function, ‘adespatial’ package, (Dray et al.,
248 2012).

249 **3. Results and Discussion**

250 **3.1 Process Performance. AD vs AcoD experiments**

251 Two consecutive experiments (E1, E2) for the start-up of both AcoD and AD were
252 successfully performed in two parallel lab-scale CSTR digesters (R1, R2). They all were
253 carried out with a stepwise increase of OLR ranging between 2.41 – 3.63 gCOD/L d. Table
254 2 summarizes the operating conditions and the removal yields obtained for all experiments.
255 --- (Table 2) ---

256 In the first run (experiment E1; 0 – 79 days), where a SS of 47.2 gCOD/L was fed, COD
257 removal efficiencies of around 50% were obtained for both co-digestion and mono-
258 digestion. In the experiment E2 (83 – 173 days of operation), where a more concentrated
259 SS was used (66.5 gCOD/L), rebounds of 11.8% and 23.2% in COD removal were
260 observed in both AcoD and AD, respectively, compared with the first run of both systems.
261 Largely, similar results were obtained in terms of VS removal and COD removed as
262 methane. (Note: a ratio of 0.38 L CH₄/gCOD at 37°C was used to calculate the removal of
263 COD as methane, COD_{CH₄}). The removal yields here presented for mono-digestion of SS
264 were in agreement with those reviewed in the literature (Astals et al., 2013; Borowski and

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265 Weatherley, 2013); in addition, the methane production rates ($0.43 - 0.61 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4}/\text{L d}$) derived
266 from Figures 2b – 3b, and the calculated specific methane production ($0.27 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4}/\text{gVS}_{\text{fed}}$)
267 were consistent with some reference values for AD of SS (Fonoll et al., 2015).
268 According to these results, no significant improvement in terms of process performance was
269 achieved when applying co-digestion with low concentrations of the co-substrate. In this
270 case, PM stands for an 8% of the feeding volume; however, it only represents some 2.1 – 3.0
271 % of COD content and 1.7 – 2.3 % of VS content. On the other hand, the higher removal
272 yields of the second set of experiments (E2) might be explained due to the higher HRT
273 applied and/or favored by the presence of an enhanced microbial consortium during the
274 second run. Other studies demonstrated this improvement when treating feedings with higher
275 TS under co-digestion (Aboudi et al., 2017) or when applying longer digestion times
276 (Appels et al., 2008).
277 Figures 2 and 3 show the main characteristics of the biogas and digestate observed
278 experimentally (methane flowrate, biogas composition, effluent total and soluble COD, VS
279 content, partial alkalinity and inorganic nitrogen). In general, all variables showed a
280 smoothly transient behavior until the system achieved the new steady state. Only the IA/TA
281 ratio, one of the key process parameters to detect acidification or overloads, increased
282 steadily during the first 40 days. It reached close values to the threshold of stability, i.e.
283 $\text{IA/TA} \leq 0.4$ (Fonolls et al., 2015). It is assumed that the step increase of OLR by 25% at
284 day 20 might have triggered this transient acidification. This effect was eventually
285 neutralized along the operation as the microbial communities purportedly adapted to the
286 new operating conditions at higher OLR. Furthermore, in the second set of experiments,
287 where the inoculum was completely adapted to work at higher OLR, the IA/TA ratio
288 remained far below the threshold of stability.

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4 289 --- (Figure 2 and 3) ---
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6 290 Finally, the quality of the inoculum was vital to accelerate the start-up process. Quick start-
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8 291 up stages, raising OLR from 2.41 to 3.45 gCOD/L d, were reached in barely 40 days, and
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10 292 validated until the steady state was fulfilled (day 79 of E1; day 173 of E2). Longer start-up
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12 293 periods would have been required if the reactor were seeded with a non-adapted inoculum.
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14 294 For instance, Maroun and El Fadel (2007) spent 293 days to achieve a stable digestion of
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16 295 municipal solid wastes at loading rate of 2.03 gVS/L d when no inoculum was fed initially.
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18 296 In other cases, when both inoculum and co-substrates come from different sources,
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20 297 acclimation periods were needed to reduce the initial VFA concentration. For instance, Janke
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22 298 et al. (2016) started up a co-digestion process to loading rates of 2.5 gVS/L d in 70 days,
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24 299 using cattle manure as inoculum to digest other agro-industrial residues.
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31 300 Based on these results, existing wastewater treatment plants treating only SS might
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33 301 assimilate the co-digestion concept and turn into centralized biogas plants. Treating small
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35 302 proportions of a non-toxic co-substrate do not affect the actual process performance in terms
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37 303 of removal efficiencies or process stability.
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41 304 **3.2. Microbial diversity: Overall description**

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43 305 A large microbial diversity was recorded and fell into 41 bacterial phyla and 4 archaeal
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45 306 phyla. Archaea represented until 4.65% relative abundance (3 samples exhibited higher
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47 307 archaeal proportion until 35% but with no replicate robustness) and almost exclusively
48
49 308 methanogenic *Euryarchaea* were retrieved. The most important bacterial phyla were
50
51 309 *Thermotogae*, *Firmicutes*, *Proteobacteria* (*Gamma-proteobacteria*) and *Synergistetes*
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53 310 (Figure 4A.). Interestingly, *Actinobacteria* and *Bacteroidetes* reported as dominant in
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55 311 anaerobic reactors (De Vrieze et al., 2017) were not retrieved at more than 2% relative
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57 312 abundance.
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313 --- (Figure 4) ---

314 A principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) based on the total community (DNA dataset, Figure
315 5A) allowed to visualize 55% of the total variation and revealed that on both dimensions,
316 reactor samples (AD and AcoD) clustered together with the inoculum samples. This result
317 indicates that the total diversity was provided mostly by the inoculum rather than by the
318 substrates (PM and SS). In addition, the samples from PM were highly different than those
319 from SS along the second dimension of the ordination. Similarly, the PCoA analysis based
320 on the active community (cDNA dataset, Figure 5B) allowed to visualize 46.8% of the total
321 variation and confirmed that on the first dimension of the ordination, reactor samples (AD
322 and AcoD) significantly clustered together with the inoculum samples and were different
323 from the feedings (Permutational ANOVA, $F=16.53$, $p\text{-value}=0.001$).

324 --- (Figure 5) ---

325 According to the performance results, applying co-digestion with low concentration of the
326 co-substrate had no apparent effect on the total and active microbial composition; therefore,
327 the crucial role of the inoculum in the process performance was confirmed.

328 While PM composition seemed to have a weak effect on the active composition of the AD or
329 AcoD assays, 444 ASVs were identified as active in PM and not active in the inoculum
330 provided. Among them, 51 ASVs (11.5%) were still active in AD and AcoD and affiliated to
331 *Clostridia* and *Negativicutes* (Blastn identity > 98%). However, they were only retrieved at
332 low relative abundance (<1%) and may not significantly affect the performance of the
333 process. These features suggested that the active microorganisms provided with the feedings
334 did not have a significant impact on the active community composition of these anaerobic
335 reactors. This is congruent with a microbial study in a UASB reactor fed with raw cheese
336 whey (Castelló et al., 2011) where the diversity was mainly provided by the inoculum. Also,

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337 Cabezas et al. (2019) showed that addition of commercial formulation increasing the fat
338 degradation did not significantly affect the microbial community composition that only
339 adapted to the experimental conditions with time. Besides, the total and active microbial
340 community were not significantly different (Clustering analysis, *Supplementary Material*,
341 Figure A.4.) which is in line with findings from De Vrieze et al. (2018), that showed a
342 significant difference between DNA and RNA-based community only for archaeal
343 communities.

344 **3.3 Active microbial diversity: AD vs AcoD experiments**

345 A PCoA associated to envfit analysis was performed on the Bray-Curtis β -diversity matrix
346 of the active microbial diversity (relative abundance) from the AD and AcoD samples. This
347 analysis aims at discriminating the AD and AcoD communities and evaluating the key
348 operational parameters that can be significantly related to the microbial community
349 composition. The two first dimensions of the PCoA represented 43% of the dataset variation
350 and showed no significant segregation between AD and AcoD (Permutational ANOVA,
351 $F=1.82$, $p\text{-value}=0.06$, Figure 6). The active microbial composition was initially linked to the
352 methane production (envfit analysis, $r^2= 0.64$, $p\text{-value}<0.01$), pointing out that the
353 community considerably changed to a more efficient methane-producing community.
354 Among the 9 ASVs that significantly changed (DESeq2, $\text{Log}_2\text{FoldChange} >25$) between the
355 first and the second experiment, all were affiliated to typical strains or sequences found in
356 anaerobic digesters (Rivière et al., 2009). Two ASVs were significantly selected during the
357 second experiment and corresponded to an acetoclastic methanogen *Methanotherix*
358 *soehngeni* (ASV329, Blastn identity=100%) and an unaffiliated taxa closed to *Oligosphaera*

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4 359 *ethanolica* (ASV6457, Blastn identity=88.8%) fermenting glucose into acetate, ethanol and
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6 360 hydrogen (Qiu et al., 2013).
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9 361 --- (Figure 6) ---
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11 362 The horseshoe distribution of the samples in the PCoA ordination reflected a gradual
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13 363 turnover of the community composition along the environmental gradient (Morton et al.,
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15 364 2017), identified as the elapsed time when a significant impact on the ordination is observed
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17 365 (envfit analysis, $r^2 = 0.54$, $p\text{-value} < 0.01$, Figure 5). The microbial composition at the
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19 366 beginning of the first run (day 0) gradually shifted towards the end of the experiment (day
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21 367 79). The strongest changes, occurred within the first 60 days, were linked to a decrease of
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23 368 ammonium concentration (envfit analysis, $r^2 = 0.30$, $p\text{-value} < 0.01$) and an increase of IA/TA
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25 369 ratio, this implying an accumulation of VFA (envfit analysis, $r^2 = 0.29$, $p\text{-value} < 0.01$). This
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27 370 shift can be associated with the progressive selection of thermophilic *Thermotogae* bacteria
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29 371 (Figure 4), which eventually became the most competitive microorganisms under the
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31 372 operating conditions here studied (Figure 4). This feature was very consistent, as the same
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33 373 pattern was observed in both the AD and AcoD experiments. These *Thermotogae* were
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35 374 mainly represented (99.5% of total *Thermotogae*) by acetate, H₂/CO₂ producers *Defluviitoga*
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37 375 bacteria (Maus et al., 2016). Hence, *Defluviitoga* bacteria may have the capacity to provide
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39 376 suitable substrates for methanogenic Archaea and five out of twenty-two *Defluviitoga* ASVs
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41 377 were positively correlated with methane production (Pearson test; $r^2 = 0.36\text{-}0.61$; $p\text{-}$
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43 378 $\text{value} < 0.01$). These 5 *Defluviitoga* ASVs were all affiliated to *Defluviitoga tunisiensis*,
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45 379 isolated from an anaerobic reactor treating whey in Tunisia (Ben Hania et al., 2012).
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47 380 Interestingly, it was currently found that *Thermotogae*'s optimum is 55°C (Ben Hania et al.,
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49 381 2012) and are dominant in thermophilic reactors (55°C) more than in mesophilic ones (Kim
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51 382 et al., 2018).
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383 At the end of the first experiment (day 79), the active microbial community was well
384 established and this mixture served as the inoculum for the second experiment (from day 83
385 to 173). This new starting community did not show the acclimation step observed during the
386 first run. The community remained stable in a similar way to other study on co-digestion
387 (Amha et al., 2017).

388 While euryarchaeal community was slightly similar between AD and AcoD (Figure 4B.), a
389 shift was identified over experimental time which turned out to be the driving factor of
390 active euryarchaeal communities (forward selection, adjusted- $r^2 = 0.16$, p-value=0.001). In
391 the first set of experiments (from day 0 to 79), active *Euryarchaea* were dominated by
392 *Methanospirillum* genus (average 86±6% of total euryarchaeal sequences) and active
393 euryarchaeota exhibited a strong decrease in terms of relative abundance of the whole
394 community, changing from 3.49% at 0 days to 0.88% at day 79. In the second set of
395 experiment, the euryarchaeal community was highly variable in terms of relative abundance
396 and composition, and was composed of both H₂/CO₂ reducer *Methanospirillum* (average
397 29±21% of total euryarchaeal sequences) and ethanol and secondary alcohol degrader
398 *Methanoculleus* (average 70±22% of total euryarchaeal sequences).

399 Finally, based on the biological evidences here presented, existing AD plants might adopt
400 the co-digestion approach without affecting the reliability of the anaerobic biocatalyst when
401 treating low concentration of a non-toxic co-substrate in the same reactor. The active
402 communities of the biocatalysts do not change significantly under co-digestion in
403 comparison with mono-digestion.

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4 **407 4. Conclusions**

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6 408 The start-up of both anaerobic digestion and co-digestion systems can achieve similar
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8 409 performances in terms of methane production, removal efficiencies or process stability when
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10 410 the co-substrate is added in low concentrations. It was demonstrated for the mono-digestion
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12 411 of sewage sludge and its co-digestion with pig manure. The study of microbial communities
13
14 412 revealed that small quantities of the co-substrate had a negligible effect on the active/total
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16 413 microbial community composition; this was mainly associated with the inoculum. Finally,
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18 414 active communities changed gradually over time as operating conditions did, but in a similar
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20 415 fashion for either anaerobic digestion or co-digestion systems.
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28 **417 Appendix A. Supplementary Material**

29 418 E-supplementary data of this work can be found in the online version of the paper.
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4 574 **Tables**

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6 575 **Table 1.** Characteristics of sewage sludge (SS) and pig manure (PM) used for the AcoD and
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8 576 AD start-up experiments (E1, E2).

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10 577 **Table 2.** Operating conditions and removal efficiencies (COD_{CH_4} , COD and VS) obtained in
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12 578 the consecutive start-up experiments (E1, E2) of AcoD (reactor R1) and AD (R2).
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21 581 **Figures**

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23 582 **Figure 1.** Schematic experimental design and sampling for molecular biology purpose. Note
24
25 583 that inoculum (Inoc) and sewage sludge (SS) were used for both anaerobic digestion (AD)
26
27 584 and co-digestion (AcoD). The AcoD consisted in a mix of inoculum, sewage sludge and 7-
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29 585 8% (vol) of pig manure (PM). Two sewage sludges were used and characterized for the first
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31 586 OLR-increase experiment (from 0 to 79 days) and for the second OLR-increase experiment
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33 587 (from 83 to 173 days), respectively, resulting in 2 sewage sludge (SS) samples in duplicates.
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41 589 **Figure 2.** AcoD Start-up. Experiment E1 (0 – 79 d) and E2 (83 – 173 d). a) OLR and
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43 590 removal efficiency in terms of COD removed as CH_4 , total COD and VS removals, b)
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45 591 methane flowrates, c) gas composition, d) effluent COD, e) effluent VS, f) pH, g) PA,TA,
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47 592 Alkalinity Ratio (IA/TA), and h) ammonium; (—) Theoretical OLR, experimental methane
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49 593 flowrate, (.....) experimental OLR, (●) COD removal efficiency, CH_4 composition, total
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51 594 COD, VS, pH, TA, and NH_4^+ , (□) VS removal efficiency, (···) COD removed as CH_4 , (○)
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53 595 CO_2 composition, soluble COD and PA, (+) IA/TA.
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4 597 **Figure 3.** AD Start-up. Experiment E1 (0 – 79 d) and E2 (83 – 173 d). a) OLR and removal
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6 598 efficiency in terms of COD removed as CH₄, total COD and VS removals, b) methane
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8 599 flowrates, c) gas composition, d) effluent COD, e) effluent VS, f) pH, g) PA,TA, Alkalinity
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10 Ratio (IA/TA), and h) ammonium; (—) Theoretical OLR, experimental methane flowrate,
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12 600 (.....) experimental OLR, (●) COD removal efficiency, CH₄ composition, total COD, VS,
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14 601 pH, TA, and NH₄⁺, (□) VS removal efficiency, (···) COD removed as CH₄, (○) CO₂
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16 602 composition, soluble COD and PA, (+) IA/TA.
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24 605 **Figure 4.** Active community dynamics over time in both anaerobic digestion (AD) and co-
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26 606 digestion (AcoD) considering the whole community and (A) euryarchaeal community (B).
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29 607 A. Barplot of the 16S rRNA transcript relative abundance over time in days showed
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31 608 separately in AD and AcoD experiments in duplicates (a and b). Phyla with relative
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33 609 abundance >1% in every sample were presented at the phylum level, and *Proteobacteria* at
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35 610 the class level. All the other minor taxa are grouped in ‘Other’ category. B. Barplot relative
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37 611 abundance of the euryarchaeal 16S rRNA transcript at the genus level over time in days
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39 612 showed separately in AD and AcoD experiments in duplicates (a and b).
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47 614 **Figure 5.** Principal coordinate analysis (A & B) using the Bray Curtis matrix distance from
48
49 615 the whole relative abundance of A. 16S rRNA transcript dataset and B. 16S rRNA gene
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51 616 amplicon dataset. Anaerobic digestion (AD) and co-digestion (AcoD) and feeding were
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53 617 plotted as color. The shape allowed visualizing the first part of the experiment with disks
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55 618 (from 0 to 79 days) and the second part of the experiment with squares (from 83 to 173
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57 619 days). On the left panel, a permutational ANOVA could be applied and underlined the
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620 significant difference between reactor samples and feedings (Permutational ANOVA,
621 $F=16.53$, $p\text{-value}=0.001$). C. Network based on the active core microbiome composed by
622 the most prevalent 151 ASVs (grey circles) identified using the *core_members* function,
623 with 50 % prevalence threshold ('microbiome' package, Lahti and Sudarshan (2012)). The
624 samples are identified by squares with the same color palette as panels A and B.

625
626 **Figure 6.** Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) using the Bray Curtis matrix distance from
627 the whole relative abundance 16S rRNA transcript dataset. Envfit was used to select the
628 significant operational parameters that correlate with the ordination (NH₄= ammonium
629 concentration in g/L, IA.TA= volatile fatty acid proportion in %, VS_rem= volatile solid
630 removal in %, Q.CH₄= methane production in L/d, OLR= organic load rate and
631 Time.cum.d= time of experiment in days). Anaerobic digestion (AD) and co-digestion
632 (AcoD) were plotted as shape and time of experiment was shown with gradient color scale.
633 The grey points represented the 53 ASVs that significantly changed between the first
634 experiment and the second experiment as measured by the log₂FoldChange estimated by the
635 differential transcript abundance (based on the negative binomial distribution, DESeq
636 function of the DESeq2 package, Love et al. (2014)). The 9 ASVs with absolute
637 Log₂FoldChange >25 were represented as a text using the ASV number and the last
638 taxonomic affiliated level.

Figure1

[Click here to download Figure: Figure1.pdf](#)

▲ DNA - $n=17$

● cDNA - $n=41$

AD

AcoD

Figure2[Click here to download Figure: Figure2.pdf](#)

Figure2 E1&E2_R1_AcoD1

Figure3

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Figure3 E1&E2 R2_AD1

Figure4[Click here to download Figure: Figure4.eps](#)

Figure5

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Figure6

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Table 1. Characteristics of sewage sludge (SS) and pig manure (PM) used for the AcoD and AD start-up experiments (E1, E2).

Parameter	SS (E1)	SS (E2)	PM
Total COD (g COD/L)	47.20	66.45	17.20
Soluble COD (g COD/L)	2.8	7.0	8.6
Total Solids (g TS/L)	35.7	58.1	11.0
Volatile Solids (g VS/L)	29.0	40.7	8.0
pH	5.92	5.65	6.45
Partial Alkalinity (g CaCO ₃ /L)	0.5	0	1.0
Total Alkalinity (g CaCO ₃ /L)	2.6	2.2	4.0
N-TKN (g/L)	2.05	2.30	1.59
N-NH ₄ ⁺ (g/L)	0.49	0.88	1.43
Methane potential (mL CH ₄ /g SV)	-	388	390
Methanogenesis (%)	-	51.7	75.2
Biodegradability (%)	-	56.2	86.6

Table 2. Operating conditions and removal efficiencies (COD_{CH₄}, COD and VS) obtained in the consecutive start-up experiments (E1, E2) of AcoD (reactor R1) and AD (R2).

Assay	Parameter	Operating conditions			PM	SS	COD _{CH₄}	COD	VS
					(% v.)	(% v.)	rem (%)	rem (%)	rem (%)
E1R1 (AcoD)	Time (d)	[0,20)	[20,40)	[40,79]	7.85	92.15	50.9	50.1	45.8
	VSLR (gVS/L d)	1.59	1.96	2.27					
	OLR (gCOD/L d)	2.41	2.98	3.45					
	HRT (d)	18.6	15.0	13.0					
E1R2 (AD)	Time (d)	[0,20)	[20,40)	[40,79]	0	100	40.9	48.3	44.7
	VSLR (gVS/L d)	1.66	2.05	2.37					
	OLR (gCOD/L d)	2.54	3.14	3.63					
	HRT (d)	18.6	15.0	13.0					
E2R1 (AcoD)	Time (d)	[83,103)	[103,123)	[123,173]	7.85	92.15	55.9	56.0	51.3
	VSLR (gVS/L d)	1.66	2.06	2.38					
	OLR (gCOD/L d)	2.41	2.98	3.45					
	HRT (d)	28.4	23.0	19.9					
E2R2 (AD)	Time (d)	[83,103)	[103,123)	[123,173]	0	100	48.4	59.5	52.5
	VSLR (gVS/L d)	1.65	2.04	2.36					
	OLR (gCOD/L d)	2.41	2.98	3.45					
	HRT (d)	30.2	24.5	21.1					